

Source: Mohammadnejad M, [Shiri M](#), Heydari M, Faghihi Z, Afshinpoor L: A Novel High Selective Colorimetric Chemosensor for Determination of Copper in Food Samples: Visual Detection. ChemistrySelect 2020, 5(43):13690-13693. [10.1002/slct.202003364](https://doi.org/10.1002/slct.202003364)

A Novel High Selective Colorimetric Chemosensor for Determination of Copper in Food Samples: Visual Detection

Masoumeh Mohammadnejad,* [Morteza Shiri](#), Masumeh Heydari, Zeinab Faghihi, and Leila Afshinpoor^[a]

[a] Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics and Chemistry Alzahra University. Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Rhodamine B hydrazide and 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde derivatives were used to synthesize novel colorimetric sensors for highly selective detection of copper ion. The measurement was based on the interaction between the synthesized ligands and Cu^{2+} and the sharp color change of the ligand from yellow to pink in the presence of Cu^{2+} increase in absorbance intensity at the new appeared absorbance peak was used as an analytical signal. The effect of parameters, such as time and sensor concentration were also investigated and discussed. The calibration curve was considered too under the optimum experimental conditions and was linear in the range $0.05\text{--}5.00\ \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The interferences of some common ions were studied and the synthetic ligand was found to be a high selective sensor. Selectivity of the proposed method makes it as an applicable technique for the determination of copper in foodstuff samples.

Keywords: Colorimetric sensors, Copper, Food sample, Rhodamine B derivatives.